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is everyone's loss**

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in financial
sector**

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Bold action against corruption

The global economy is in a severe depression inflicted by the massive financial crisis and an acute loss of confidence. This global recession caused banks to undergo structural adjustment and thousands of companies were forced to close down their businesses. As a result millions of people are currently unemployed, or are forced to take contracts instead of full-time positions.

In addition, the IMF declared that global activity is projected to decline by 1.3 percent this year as a whole before rising modestly during the course of 2010.

In such scenario, businesses are facing political and investment risks, and governments are searching plausible and durable answers to secure a fast recovery: a solution that, however, seems to still be far.

This turmoil is even more worrying when considering the "purchasing power" of corruption. To survive this crisis, many companies find bribery as an attractive option to win competitive bids. In such condition, where the imperative is to regain the lost ground, bribes can be used as a form of unfair competition.

The 2008 Global Corruption Barometer, a research paper published by Transparency International, observes that the impact of the financial crisis has increased people's fear of corruption among private companies. In 2004, approximately 53 percent out of 73,000 respondents from 69 countries saw the private sector as being corrupt, up from 45 percent in 2004. One fifth of the countries where the survey was conducted said that private sectors are more corrupted than others. But the public sector is also at stake. In total 69 percent of respondents said political parties were corrupt, the same as four years ago.

Two months ago, despite this foggy landscape, the chief executives from some of the most leading companies signed a letter to Secretary General, Ban Ki-moon to support the fight against corruption.

In a momentous step for the world financial system, this unprecedented move could represent a new manifesto for our economy. And we have to take bold action to make this happen.

Sandro Calvani
UNICRI Director

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An Analysis of Mexico's Organized Crime:

narco-police and the dead women of Juárez

**Un análisis del crimen
organizado en México**

los narcopolicías y la muertas de Juárez

* Wael Hikal

The current situation in Mexico has put the international community on alert due to the increase in crime rates; besides common criminality, bizarre behaviours have developed and are concerning Mexican citizens, their government and foreigners. This situation is out of the country's control: in the past, attacks, massive kidnappings and homicides, as well as drug trafficking, were seen as isolated cases, but nowadays they have become recurrent and interconnected issues.

Criminologist Rafael Garófalo recognizes that criminality is an evolutionary phenomenon and that robbery and murder are deeply entrenched in human nature (Hikal, 2009). Nowadays, homicides have become a "normal" event, in the sense that it is no longer surprising to see portrayed in the media dead military, police officers, heads of government, or even their opposing parties (the so-called "narco-police" or "narco-military"). Moreover, the political contribution has allowed crime to develop territorially, reaching regional and international levels.

Territoriality continues to be the main work area for organized crime and, in a global economy, the geography of crime grows exponentially. Local criminal organizations are presented with new international opportunities on an almost daily basis (Napo-

leoni, 2008). Globalization and economic growth have strongly promoted the transformation of crime beyond national borders in every part of the world. The improvements in communication and information technology have overcome national boundaries, with increased mobility of people, goods and services around the world, while the rise of the global economy has moved crime beyond its domestic base (Calvani, 2008).

Historically, the events that caused major "terror" in Mexico began with the progressive disappearance of women in the city of Juárez (in the Mexican state of Chihuahua); one after another, these women became invisible to the local citizens and

to the judicial authorities in particular, which caused a great loss of confidence in the administration of the justice system. At the time, they were founding naked bodies of women with visible lesions and signs of sexual abuse; the fact that women were the

La actual situación de México ante la perspectiva de los demás países ha puesto en alerta la seguridad internacional debido al incremento de la criminalidad, que más allá de ser una criminalidad común, ha desarrollado conductas bizarras que tienen preocupados a los ciudadanos mexicanos, a sus dirigentes y a los turistas. Esta situación se ha salido de las posibilidades de control en el País, en parte porque no estábamos acostumbrados a una situación de este tipo pues los casos de atentados, secuestros y homicidios masivos, así como de narcotráfico eran sino aislados, no tan continuos e interconectados como lo vivimos ahora.

Ya el criminólogo Rafael

Garófalo vislumbrara que la criminalidad es un fenómeno evolutivo y que lo más arraigado en la naturaleza humana son el robo y el homicidio. Hoy en día, los homicidios han pasado a ser un hecho "normal", pues ya no es de extrañarse ver en

los medios de comunicación militares, policías y directivos de gobierno muertos, así como sus contrapartes, los llamados "narcopolicías" y "narcomilitares", además de las ayudas de políticos para que la criminalidad se desarrolle con fluidez en un territorio, que abarca desde lo regional hasta lo internacional. La territorialidad sigue siendo la suprema área de trabajo para el crimen organizado, y en una economía globalizada la geografía del crimen se amplía exponencialmente. Las organizaciones criminales locales son presentadas con nuevas oportunidades internacionales casi diariamente (Napoleoni, 2008). La globalización y el crecimiento económico han promovido fuertemente la transformación del crimen más allá de las fronteras en el mundo. El mejoramiento de las comunicaciones y la información tecnológica ha desbordado los límites nacionales con mayor movilidad de las personas, bienes y servicios alrededor del mundo, y el emerger de la economía globalizada ha movido al crimen más allá de su base doméstica (Calvani, 2008). Históricamente los hechos que han causado mayor "terror" en el país mexicano comienzan con mujeres que poco a poco fueron desapareciendo. El territorio al que se hace referencia es Ciudad de Juárez, Estado de Chihuahua (México), donde

only victims of these crimes led this phenomenon to be labelled *las muertas de Juárez* (ed. the dead women of Juárez). These events triggered a series of protests from the citizens who were complaining about their women: daughters, sisters, girlfriends, wives and sisters in law. Similarly, it also caused the media to express its theories on the matter in a series of documentaries and movies which portray the impunity, the corruption, the lies, the trafficking in human beings, the exploitation, the violence and the sexual abuse suffered. The impact was so great that the National Council of Science and Technology and the local government of Chihuahua invested in a DNA data bank (CONACYT, 2008).

Another point, closely related to the previous, is that organized crime in Mexico has become an intimidating phenomenon, dangerous and almost terrorist, intended as causing terror (Félix Tapia, 2005). This is the effect it has had on citizens, on the police, on the military, on directors and secretaries of security; even though the latter are deeply entrenched in acts of corruption, the opposing party has become involved in their kidnappings, torture and homicides throughout the entire Mexican territory, and there are states in which even mayors have been murdered. The involvement of the police and the military in drug trafficking has become an inextricable factor: policemen providing protection to cartel leaders, soldiers supplying weapons, transportation for illicit merchandise, as well as providing support during kidnappings, extortions, selling of drugs, counterfeit clothes and other goods, among other activities. It is incredible to see in the media how national security forces are violated at the time when they are shown decapitated, tied up, with their heads missing, or with the so-called *tiro de gracia* (ed. kill shot) in their heads. During 2007 and 2008 there were a series of murders targeting the police in the municipality of San Nicolás De Los Garza, in the Mexican state of Nuevo León; they were kidnapped and their lives were taken at any hour and in any place, but the case still remains unsolved.

una tras otra se volvían invisibles para los ciudadanos pero sobre todo para las autoridades judiciales, lo que provocó una grave desconfianza en el sistema de administración de la justicia. Al mismo tiempo se fueron encontrando cuerpos

de mujeres desnudas y con aparentes signos de lesiones y violación, que por el hecho de ser sólo mujeres dio lugar a que a éste fenómeno se le diera el título de: "Las muertas de Juárez". Tales hechos han dado lugar a una serie de protestas por parte de los ciudadanos que reclamaban a sus mujeres: hijas, esposas, novias, hermanas, cuñadas. Los mismos hechos que dieron lugar a que los medios de comunicación expresaran sus teorías mediante programas documentales y películas que revelan la impunidad, la corrupción, la mentira, el tráfico de personas, la explotación, la violación, los trastornos sexuales y parafilias. Tal fue el impacto que ocasionó que al Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología se le hizo una propuesta por parte del gobierno de Chihuahua para invertir en un banco de datos de ADN (CONACYT, 2008).

Por otro lado, y estrechamente relacionado con lo anterior, el crimen organizado en México ha sido un fenómeno intimidante, peligroso y casi terrorista, si se entiende al terrorismo como causar terror (Félix Tapia, 2005), y tal ha sido el efecto en los ciudadanos, en los policías, militares, directores y secretarios de seguridad, que a pesar de que a

los anteriores se les relaciona estrechamente con actos de corrupción, la contraparte es que en casi todo el territorio mexicano se ha dado a conocer el secuestro, la tortura y el homicidio de éstos. Hay Estados mexicanos en el que se han asesinado incluso a los presidentes municipales.

La participación de la policía y los militares en el narcotráfico ha sido un factor inseparable: los policías que brindan protección a los líderes narcotraficantes, los militares que proporcionan armas, el transporte de mercancía ilícita, así como el secuestro, la extorsión, la venta de drogas, ropa y materiales falsos, entre otros. Es increíble ver en los medios

There is no doubt that the country needs a moment of peace during which local governments and their citizens can relax. But the situation worsened in the beginning of 2009, when the economic recession started taking hold. Criminally-speaking, poverty, lack of education and unemployment are all risk factors that fuel crime as a way to escape these aforementioned aspects; organized crime employs and trains all these types of people to carry out illegal activities. To reduce these phenomena, it is necessary that States, and Mexico in particular, urgently apply the international tools to fight organized crime, human trafficking, terrorism, drug abuse and other criminal activities. This means countering them not only with the use of force, but also with a good penitentiary administration that addresses the root causes of criminality, that provides a treatment and makes room for restorative justice, that pays attention to the victims and that develops prevention programmes.

Among these above-mentioned tools, there are also the Compendium of United Nations standards and norms in crime prevention and criminal justice (UNODC, 2007), International Terrorism and Governmental Structures (UNICRI, 2005), Eliminating Violence Against Women: Forms, Strategies and Tools (UNICRI, 2008), Criminal Justice Assessment Toolkit (UNODC, 2006), The Threat of Narco-trafficking in the Americas (UNODC, 2008), Toolkit to Combat Trafficking in Persons (UNODC, 2007). In this list can also be included the studies and publications issued by the various offices, institutes, centres and agencies of the UN. Mexico definitely requires international support to reduce its high levels of criminality, or it runs the risk of reaching the extreme levels of some other countries.

* Wael Hikal, President of the Mexican Society of Criminology of the State of Nuevo León (NGO), Director of the journal Criminology, Forensics Sciences, and Private Security.

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de comunicación cómo las fuerzas defensoras de un país también son vulneradas apareciendo decapitados, amarrados y con sus cabezas extraviadas, y en algunas ocasiones con el llamado "tiro de gracia". Durante el 2007 y 2008, una serie de homicidios contra policías ocurrieron en el municipio de San Nicolás de Los Garza, Estado de Nuevo León (México), en donde los policías constantemente y en cualquier lugar eran secuestrados y privados de la vida. Muchos de ellos, casos que quedan sin resolver.

No hay duda de que el país requiere un estado de paz, en el que los gobiernos y sus ciudadanos encuentren una salida a dicha condición. A inicios del 2009 la situación empeora cuando comienza el fenómeno de la recesión, pues criminológicamente la pobreza, la falta de educación y el desempleo son factores de riesgo que alimentan la criminalidad mientras que ésta emplea y capacita a todo tipo de sujetos para llevar a cabo diversas actividades ilícitas. Con miras a reducir el fenómeno es urgente que los países, y en especial México, apliquen las herramientas internacionales para combatir el tráfico de personas, el terrorismo, el abuso de drogas y demás conductas criminales. No sólo combatir con la fuerza dará resultado, sino que además se requiere de un buen sistema legislativo y una administración penitenciaria más efectiva que analice las causas de la criminalidad, que ofrezca un tratamiento, que de lugar a la justicia restaurativa, que atienda a las víctimas y desarrolle programas de prevención.

Entre las herramientas bibliográficas a las que se hace referencia anteriormente, se encuentran la Recopilación de Reglas y Normas de las Naciones Unidas en la Esfera de la Prevención del Delito y la Justicia Penal (UNODC, 2007), Terrorismo Internacional y Estructuras Gubernamentales (UNICRI, 2005), Eliminación de la Violencia contra la Mujer: formas, estrategias y herramientas (UNICRI, 2008), Manual de Justicia Criminal (UNODC, 2006), La amenaza del Narcotráfico en las Américas (UNODC, 2008) y el Manual para la Lucha contra la Trata de Personas (UNODC, 2007). A la lista anterior, cabe sumar los estudios y publicaciones que realizan las diversas oficinas, institutos, centros y agencias de las Naciones Unidas en el mundo. Estos constituyen una de las tantas vías y ayudas en las que un pueblo, en este caso el mexicano, puede apoyarse junto con la asistencia internacional para reducir definitivamente sus altos índices de criminalidad antes de arribar como ya ha sucedido con otros países, a extremos incontrolables de muerte y terror.

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